

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and the Notion of 2-Dimensional Targets

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In (1), we argued that sometimes interactions are linked to both numbers and vectors. An example is a free particle which has both p (momentum vector) and E (energy number). Mathematically, one cannot add a number to a vector and so in (1) we suggested that linking equations need to use a dot product which is linked to orientation in the problem. One may then try to deconstruct the dot product to obtain an equation with variables directly linked to an interaction (linear E , linear p) and orientation matrices. This seems to be the approach used by Dirac in deconstructing the Klein-Gordon equation into a linear form.

In this note, we revisit the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case which follows from the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + pc \cdot pc = -m_0^2 c^4$ (or its Klein-Gordon version). We note that in the rest frame there is only a number $m_0 c^2$, but in the moving frame there exists a number E and a vector p in some direction. The $p \cdot p$ dot product maps p to a number.

We suggest that a key idea here (the idea of special relativity) is the equivalence of the two frames (rest and moving) and that this forces one to deal with a number and vector in one frame as being equivalent to only a number in the other (rest frame). Thus, analysis in special relativity is very different from that of nonrelativistic physics. Here we suggest that one should be able to directly relate p (vector) and E in one frame to $m_0 c^2$ in the rest frame, as these are the physical variables which apply to an interaction. It is the linear form of p which is proportional to impulse, not $p \cdot p$. This seems to imply that one must create a dot product using p , but not $p \cdot p$. At the same time, $b \cdot p$ must yield $(b \cdot p) (b \cdot p) = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$. This means that b must be a vector of matrices. (We simplify here by only considering the p vector.) The point we wish to make is that if there is a matrix, it must operate on a vector and this vector must represent some kind of physical property of the particle. No such vector is seen in nonrelativistic physics, although spin exists in the nonrelativistic world. If that is the case, one could dispense with the matrices and simply introduce three vectors linked with p_x, p_y, p_z . These would seem to be the well-known $(1,0,0)$, $(0,1,0)$ and $(0,0,1)$ vectors. In such a case, there is no notion of spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

In (1) we argued that an equation linking E, p (linear) to m_0 must describe interactions. In fact, E and p in their linear form are the variables associated with an interaction. The main point we wish to make in this note, is that p_x, p_y, p_z are proportional to impulse hits on planes (2 dimensional objects) perpendicular to the $x, y,$ and z axis. Thus, if one is interested in describing the physical hits, then given a particle moving in the z axis, one may define a 2-vector $(1,0)$. This particle should strike an x - y plane, but mathematically such a plane is defined by $(x,y) = x+iy$. In other words, using complex numbers one may use 2 dimensional vectors because these describe the physical planes of impulse hits for p_x, p_y, p_z . In particular, x must be perpendicular to z , i.e. $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$ and then y is described by $(0,i)$.

We argue that this is the reason that 2-vectors are introduced as properties of a particle (linked to 2×2 matrices) instead of the usual $(1,0,0), (0,1,0), (0,0,1)$. In other words, the two dimensional nature of a spinor is directly related to the two dimensional nature of a target associated with any p component. Thus, it is the 2-vector picture which describes interactions, i.e. the physics of the problem and this gives rise to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ formalism.

Vectors and Numbers

We noted in (1) that one may have interaction variables such as the number E (free particle energy) and p (momentum vector) which describe an interaction. Unfortunately, one cannot add a number to a vector. In order to obtain an equation relating the two, we argued in (1) that one must introduce an appropriate dot product. An obvious example is $p \cdot p$, but other physical dot products exist in different problems such as the dot product with a normal to a surface through which particles/photons pass. As a result, one may obtain a number equation such as the Lorentz invariant:

$$-E^2 + p \cdot p c^2 = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1))$$

The Importance of Special Relativity

Special relativity links different frames. For example, one may have a particle at rest in one frame, i.e. $E=m_0 c^2$ and $p=0$. This implies there is no orientation whatsoever in the rest frame. A moving frame (in any direction with constant $-v$), however, gives rise to $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and a p vector. This leads to the unusual result of a number, $m_0 c^2$, being equivalent to a number, $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ together with a vector p . Mathematically it is difficult to write such an equivalence unless one uses p in a dot product which is exactly what is done in (1). The problem with (1) is that one has quadratic variables, while physically an interaction is described by linear variables. In particular, impulse of $p=(p_x, p_y, p_z)$ is proportional to the component of p perpendicular to the surface. For example, p_z is proportional to the impulse against an x - y plane.

As a result, one may argue for an equation which links E, p to $m_0 c^2$, but only uses linear variables as these represent interactions. P is a vector and so it seems one must introduce a dot product to map it to a number. If one uses $b \cdot p$, then one must have:

$$(b \cdot p) (b \cdot p) = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z \quad ((2))$$

This means that b cannot be a number, it must be a matrix, namely an anticommuting one. It is already known (2), that 2×2 Pauli matrices suffice for b . In a more general calculation, one would use 4×4 matrices as Dirac did, but we retain the 2×2 matrices for simplicity. We do not wish to focus on the matrices here, but rather on their associated vectors.

It is known that a matrix acts on a vector, thus there must be a vector associated with the particle and this must represent some kind of physical property, presumably one that was not generally known in nonrelativistic mechanics (before the Stern-Gerlach experiment).

If a particle has three vectors associated with p_x, p_y, p_z (to allow for $p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$) then one may ignore the matrices altogether it seems and choose vectors which yield the result ((2)). The immediate choice seems to be:

$$(1,0,0) \quad (0,1,0) \quad (0,0,1) \quad ((3))$$

With the choice of ((3)), there are no matrices and no spin $\frac{1}{2}$. The question then becomes: What is the issue with this viewpoint?

We argued in Part I that one wishes to describe physical interactions in an equation. Thus, although the vectors ((3)) ensure orthogonality, one must describe p_x striking a y - z plane, p_y striking an x - z plane and p_z striking an x - y plane. Planes are two dimensional objects and we argue that this is key to the use of 2×2 Pauli matrices or spin vectors of dimension 2.

In particular, if one describes a particle moving in the z direction by the 2 vector $(1,0)$ instead of $(0,0,1)$, then using the Pauli matrices (2):

$$S_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad S_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad S_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad ((4))$$

one has: $p_x(0,1) + p_y(0,i) + p_z(1,0)$ ((5))

One may see that given $(1,0)$ representing a particle moving in the z direction, it strikes an (x,y) plane. Mathematically, the (x,y) plane may be written as $x+iy$, with x being perpendicular to $(1,0)$. Thus, $(0,1)$ should represent the x direction and $(0, i)$ the y direction. This leads to 2 vectors instead of three vectors ((3)) because one wishes to describe the interaction planes, not simply orthogonality.

One may note that taking the complex conjugate transpose of ((5)) and multiplying by ((5)) yields:

$$P_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z \quad ((6))$$

As a result, we argue that 2 vectors (spinors) arise through an attempt to describe the orientation of interactions associated with (p_x, p_y, p_z) . Each p component strikes a 2×2 plane and so one only needs 2 vectors to describe orientation if one uses $(x,y)=x+iy$ which is standard. ((3)) which represents 3-vectors, although representing orthogonality does contain the information of impulse hits against 2 dimensional planes. Thus, spin $\frac{1}{2}$ is a consequence of the impulse hits against 2 dimensional planes, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the 2 vector nature of spinors follows directly from trying to describe the physics of interactions of (p_x, p_y, p_z) for a free particle. Each p_i interacts with a 2 dimensional plane consisting of the other two variables. For example, p_z strikes an x - y plane. Such a plane is described by (x,y) for a fixed z , but mathematically $(x,y)=x+iy$. Thus, one does not need 3 orthogonal vectors $(1,0,0)$, $(0,1,0)$, $(0,0,1)$ even though these contain the proper orthogonality. These vectors do not describe the physics of impulse hits which is what one wishes to demonstrate. One rather needs to use $(1,0)$ (example) representing a particle moving in the z direction, $(0,1)$ an orthogonal vector representing the x direction and $(0, i)$ representing the y direction because $(x,y)=x+iy$. We argue that this is at the root of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ for a free particle, but that there is a second principle at work. This principle is the special relativistic one which equates a rest frame with a number $m_0 c^2$ (and no orientation whatsoever) with an

$E = \gamma m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and a \mathbf{p} which is a vector. To link these variables one must introduce a dot product. The common linking equation is $-\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} c^2 = -m_0^2 c^4$, the Lorentz invariant. One, however, should be able to link the interaction variables E, \mathbf{p}, m_0 which are linear. This requires a dot product for \mathbf{p} , i.e. $\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, but if $(\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{p}) (\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{p}) = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$, \mathbf{b} must be a matrix and not numbers. These matrices act on vectors and so we focus entirely on the vectors in this note. We argue that they must represent a physical property, but at the same time one must describe the physics of the interactions that occur. Given that a p_z strikes an x - y plane, we suggest that one must explicitly use 2-vectors and not 3-vectors to describe these interactions. This gives rise to spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

References

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2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pauli_matrices